

Research Article

Transition Process in Inclusive Education: Predicaments and Interventions

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Abstract

The study addressed the process of transitioning to inclusive education, with a particular focus on the difficulties and strategies used by public elementary school teachers in the city schools division of Dasmariñas. Purposive sampling was used to choose 135 public school teachers, including SNED and inclusive education teachers, in the study, utilizing a descriptive quantitative design. A validated self-made survey checklist was used to collect the data, and descriptive and inferential statistics were used for analysis. The findings showed that teacher-led interventions had a major effect on children's behavioral and academic growth. The execution of the intervention was shown to be significantly influenced by age, with older instructors exhibiting more faithfulness. Although issues like scarce resources and big class sizes were frequently mentioned in teacher profiles, they had a modest impact on perceived efficacy rather than a considerable impact on implementation level. A cyclical, integrated intervention model was proposed, emphasizing fidelity enhancement, challenge mitigation, continuous monitoring, and stakeholder collaboration. The findings offer practical implications for strengthening inclusive education practices and policies.

Keywords: Inclusive Education, Transition Process, Learners with Special Educational Needs (LSENs), Teacher-led Interventions, Implementation Fidelity.

Introduction

Inclusive education has come to be an important approach in support of the learning of all students in an education system around the world, which includes learners with special educational needs (LSENs) having the opportunity to avail a quality education. In addressing the need is employing inclusive education for all wherein it includes students with special educational needs in mainstream type of classrooms regardless of physical, intellectual, or emotional needs. Due to the methods of teaching, inclusive education serves as a foundation for promoting equality and empowerment at the elementary stage (Pradhan and Naik, 2024), and every child should benefit from an inclusive environment that promotes well-being. The model simultaneously about adapting teaching methods, curricula and assessment systems to adequately include students with disabilities in the educational process and guarantee that students with disabilities can be actively included in all curricular programs. This approach corresponds with the global frameworks, as previously explored by Bessarab *et al.*, (2023) have cited the significance of interventions and methods that facilitate the transition of learners with special educational needs to be involved in the general education classrooms.

In the local context of the Philippines, inclusive education in the Philippines has become a priority; however, there is still a need for enhancement in its implementation, particularly in how teachers cater to the academic and behavioral needs of LSENs. On top of the transition process from specialized education programs (SPED) to an inclusive classroom is significant in the experience of learners with special educational needs (LSENs). The importance of the process relies on its potential to provide the skills and experiences to cope in a regular setting, yet a transition from SPED to mainstreamed inclusive classrooms can bring many challenges for students and teachers. But the process is important because it has the potential to provide these students with the tools and knowledge needed to thrive in general education classrooms.

Adaptivity plays an essential role in successful inclusive transitions as both teachers and students need to adjust to new classroom dynamics, learning strategies, and social environments, cited by Then and Pohlmann-Rother (2024). Teachers play an important role within the transition process, as they must cater to and address students' diverse needs, ensuring that every learner receives the academic and social support they require. Mays *et al.*, (2020) elaborate importance of smooth transitions for children with disabilities (CWDs) who need support across all educational stages. They stress how educator readiness and appropriate response strategies are key components of a successful transition from a special education program to an inclusive setting. Despite the interventions, teachers face significant challenges in managing the transition process that may impede the effective integration of LSENs into inclusive classrooms.

Teachers face a variety of challenges, especially those who handle LSENs in an inclusive classroom therefore which hinders the success of the transition process. Ngadni *et al.*, (2023) explore different challenges that teachers may face when working in inclusive early childhood education environments, such as managing the varied needs of their students, a lack of adequate resources, and insufficient teacher training. These challenges increase the teachers' burden with the lack of skills and support required to respond to academic, including the behavioral and emotional needs of their students, which highly impact the learning environment between teachers and students. The challenge of meeting the varied needs of students can result in frustration for both teachers and students can negatively influence the educational experience. Mabanag *et al.*, (2024) urge the concept of teacher readiness as they point out that many teachers have not equipped themselves with specialized knowledge and are not engaged in ongoing professional development activities to handle specific instruction in meeting the needs of LSENs. Additionally, the lack of resources, including teaching aids or specialized support personnel, can burden teachers in maintaining an inclusive classroom environment.

Consequently, interventions serve a vital role in the transition of LSENs from SPED to inclusive classrooms is essential in addressing academic, behavioral, and emotional needs as teachers employ various interventions to improve the transition, aiming to improve students' academic performance, ensuring the learners' inclusion within the classroom setting, at the same time facing additional challenges. Furthermore, Perera (2024) recognizes techniques applied by teachers in an inclusive classroom, such as engagement-based differentiation, individualized support plans, and implementation of assistive technology, etc. In addressing the specific needs of LSENs, these interventions can also be implemented as a proactive step in developing an inclusive and tolerant educational setting. In line with that, Dada *et al.*, (2023) discuss targeted interventions for students with severe disabilities to support well-structured interventions addressing their academic and emotional needs. These interventions are essential throughout the transition because they guarantee that students are not left behind and with adequate resources in an inclusive environment.

While global and national interventions are available, the need for more studies in the local context of Dasmariñas, Cavite, persists and is essential for improving inclusive education in the region. Teacher transitions have seen the least amount of research when compared to the available data and research on inclusive education in both local and international settings and understanding the local context of teachers' actions, as well as the impacts of the initiatives that they undertook during the transition phase is important for improving the adoption of inclusive education practices, especially in Dasmariñas, Cavite. Based on the context, it aims to contribute by evaluating the level of challenges faced by SPED and inclusive education teachers, the strategies used for these challenges, and the effectiveness of these interventions. And through the perspectives of public SPED and receiving teachers in Dasmariñas, this study hopes to contribute valuable insights for local educational planning, teacher training initiatives, and resource management in support of the transition of LSENs through inclusive classrooms. The purpose of this study is based on the need to improve the transition experience from the perspective of teachers in an inclusive education setting. In recognition of the challenges and effective interventions will be vital as global and local education systems champion inclusive education and seek to ensure learners with special educational needs (SENs) are meaningfully included in mainstream classrooms. Filling in the gaps in the literature on inclusive education, addressing the potential barriers, and effective strategies will have practical implications for teacher practices, support systems, and policy changes needed to ensure all students, regardless of their different needs that can thrive in inclusive educational settings.

Review of Literature

Impact of Teacher Demographics on Inclusive Education

The transition of learners with special educational needs (SENs) into mainstream classrooms is shaped by several teacher-related factors, particularly demographics such as age, sex, position, and years of service.

These demographic characteristics influence teachers' beliefs, attitudes, and competence, which in turn determine the success of inclusive education programs. Woodcock and Hardy (2023) emphasized that teachers' self-efficacy strongly correlates with their willingness and ability to adapt teaching practices for diverse learners. Teachers with higher self-efficacy are more inclined to employ inclusive strategies, while those with lower confidence may limit their implementation. Importantly, self-efficacy often develops from years of service and professional development, suggesting that demographic characteristics and experience are interwoven with effective inclusive practices.

Teacher profiling has also been linked to the efficient use of resources and the tailoring of professional development programs. Albion *et al.*, (2015) highlighted that aligning training in information and communication technology (ICT) with teachers' competencies and classroom contexts maximizes resource deployment and instructional effectiveness. Similarly, Tabassum and Nayak (2021) underscored the role of gender in shaping pedagogical choices, revealing how gendered assumptions and stereotypes influence teaching practices, particularly in resource use and instructional methods. Further, Izquierdo *et al.*, (2025) found that professional experience enhances teachers' psychological well-being and self-efficacy, but structured programs focused on resilience and emotional intelligence can reduce disparities, ensuring teachers of varying ages and experiences maintain effectiveness in inclusive settings.

Inclusive Education and Student Outcomes

Inclusive education has been recognized globally as a framework that fosters equitable learning opportunities and psychosocial development. Kausik and Hussain (2023) reported that students with learning disabilities in inclusive classrooms demonstrated greater academic motivation, self-efficacy, and well-being compared to those in segregated environments. These findings affirm that inclusive strategies can cultivate both academic and personal growth. Capangpangan *et al.*, (2023) further emphasized that teacher preparation and institutional support are critical for implementing inclusive practices, as training, professional development, and prior experience directly influence their success. In the Philippine context, inclusive education has been steadily implemented to address the needs of learners with disabilities. Muega (2016) documented the shift from segregated special education (SPED) programs to inclusive models, which integrate learners with special needs into mainstream classrooms. Despite challenges, the perspectives of teachers, administrators, and parents reveal a collective drive for inclusivity, reflecting a national commitment to equitable education.

Enhancing Academic Performance and Behavioral Development of LSENS

Efforts to strengthen academic performance and behavioral development among learners with special educational needs (LSENS) have focused on multisensory learning, restorative practices, and professional development for educators. Multisensory support, which incorporates visual, auditory, tactile, and kinesthetic elements, has been proven effective in enhancing retention and engagement. Shams and Seitz (2008) and Harrison and Patel (2023) reported that such approaches foster deeper understanding and long-term learning. Supporting this, Rau *et al.*, (2020) and Bas *et al.*, (2021) demonstrated that multisensory strategies reduce distractions, increase motivation, and inspire students to develop lifelong learning skills. Behavioral interventions in schools have also shifted from punitive methods to restorative approaches. The Child Health and Development Institute of Connecticut (2024) highlighted how restorative practices reduce suspensions and improve student behavior by focusing on relationships and underlying issues. CT Insider (2024) echoed these findings, reporting that schools adopting restorative approaches experienced fewer disruptions and greater engagement.

In terms of academic growth, Tuero *et al.*, (2022) found that school-based training in self-regulation strategies significantly improved students' performance across multiple subjects, underscoring the importance of structured interventions. Obee *et al.*, (2022) added that professional development in classroom management and behavioral support equips teachers to foster more positive and productive learning environments, ultimately benefiting both academic and social outcomes. Professional learning remains a cornerstone of teacher effectiveness. Makhmetova *et al.*, (2023) emphasized that both formal and informal learning experiences enhance teachers' adaptability in executing interventions. Similarly, Cabahug *et al.*, (2024) and Uzorka *et al.*, (2024) confirmed that professional development consistently improves teaching quality and student achievement, regardless of teacher role, experience, or qualification. However, systemic challenges persist. Bakar *et al.*, (2022) and Kim and Kim (2023) reported that teachers across contexts face comparable issues such as workload, classroom management, and balancing administrative with instructional responsibilities. These findings suggest that institutional support systems must be inclusive and comprehensive, addressing challenges experienced universally across teacher demographics.

Results and Discussion

Demographic Profile of Public Teachers in the Division of Dasmariñas, Cavite as to Age, School, Designation, Length of Service

Table 1. Distribution of the respondents as to age.

Age	Frequency	Percentage
20–30 years old	25	18.5
31–40 years old	55	40.7
41–50 years old	43	31.9
51 years old and above	12	8.9
Grand total	135	100.0

Table 1 shows the distribution of the respondents by age which are categorized as to age ranges in the table presented above. As seen from the table, a total of four (4) age ranges were used to categorize the public-school teachers that were chosen as the respondents of the study.

Based on the data gathered from the respondents, majority of the public-school teachers belonged to the age range of 31–40 years old which obtained a frequency of 55 or 41.0%. This signifies that most of the chosen respondents of the study were among the age bracket of young adults. While, the least number of respondents belonged to the age range of 51 years old and above which had a frequency of 12 or 9.0%. This means that the minority of the respondents falls under the age bracket of middle-aged adults to old adults. Overall, the data reveal that the respondents are evenly distributed across the predetermined age ranges, with each category being adequately represented.

Table 2. Distribution of the respondents as to school.

School	Frequency	Percentage
Bautista Elementary School	30	22.2
Dr. Jose Rizal Elementary School	28	20.7
Francisco E. Barzaga Memorial School	32	23.7
Salawag Elementary School	20	14.8
Sta. Cruz Elementary School	25	18.5
Grand total	135	100.0

The distribution of the respondents by school is presented in Table 2 which shows the schools that are chosen within the locale of the study. As seen on the table, the chosen public schools that are within the locality of Dasmariñas, Cavite are Bautista Elementary School, Dr. Jose Rizal Elementary School, Francisco E. Barzaga Memorial School, Salawag Elementary School, and Sta. Cruz Elementary School. Considering the data gathered from the respondents of the study, it was found out that majority of the public-school teachers were employed in Francisco E. Barzaga Memorial School which gained a frequency of 32 or 24.0%. Whereas, the minority of the respondents were employed in Salawag Elementary School which had a frequency of 20 or 15.0%. The result signifies that each of the schools that were chosen to participate in the study were also well-represented considering that each of the respondents in each school are close in frequency based on the data presented in the table. This also indicates that since the respondents are well distributed among the chosen schools for the study, resource sharing and collaborative efforts may be evident among these educational institutions.

Table 3. Distribution of the respondents as to designation.

Designation	Frequency	Percentage
Teacher I	42	31.1
Teacher II	18	13.3
Teacher III	25	18.5
SPET I	36	26.7
SPET II	9	6.7
SPET III	3	2.2
Master teacher I	1	0.7
Master teacher II	1	0.7
Grand total	135	100.0

The designation of the respondents of the study are categorized as to Teacher I, Teacher II, Teacher III, SPET I, SPET II, SPET III, Master Teacher I, and Master Teacher II which are all presented in Table 3. Based on the data gathered from the respondents of the study, majority of the respondents have a designation of Teacher I considering a frequency of 42 which represents 31.1% of the total number of respondents of the study. While, the minority of the study were designated as Master Teacher I and Master Teacher II in which one (1) public-school teacher falls under in each of the designation and was only comprised of 0.7% of the total number of respondents of the study. The categorization of the designation of the respondents of the study shows a diverse range of roles that are present within the chosen educational institutions of the study. Moreover, the variety of designations implies a structured hierarchy and specialization within the teaching workforce of the educational institutions stated in this study.

Table 4. Distribution of the respondents as to length of service.

Length of service	Frequency	Percentage
1–12 years	96	71.1
13–24 years	33	24.4
25–36 years	4	3.0
37–49 years	2	1.5
Grand total	135	100.0

Table 4 highlights the distribution of the respondents by the number of years in their current position. The number of years in the current position of the respondents are presented by pre-determined ranges which are shown in the table above. Based on the data gathered from the respondents, majority were working in their field of expertise for 1–12 years since this gained the greatest number of responses from the respondents which are represented by a frequency of 96 or 71.1%. While the least number of respondents have been working as teachers for 37–49 years which obtained a frequency of 2 or 1.5%. This distribution suggests that most teachers are in the early to mid-stages of their careers. This demographic could have implications for professional development programs, mentoring needs, and the overall experience level within the educational system.

Interventions Employed by Teachers During Transition Process as to Academic Performance and Behavioral Environment

Table 5. Interventions employed as to academic performance.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) I regularly incorporate students' interest into my lesson planning to increase engagement.	3.36	0.592	Often
2) I implement structured step-by-step instructions with visuals for students to support complex tasks.	3.33	0.584	Often
3) I provide one-on-one tutoring support to students who struggle with the content.	3.28	0.607	Often
4) I incorporate extra and flexible time on activities, tests and assignments.	3.32	0.631	Often
5) I use visual aids to enhance retention and understanding in support to diverse learners.	3.38	0.621	Often
6) I use adaptive software to facilitate smoother transitions for students with disabilities.	2.94	0.826	Often
7) I incorporate oral presentation as alternative assessment for students to demonstrate their knowledge.	3.33	0.678	Often
8) I implement flexible seating arrangements to accommodate students' needs.	3.33	0.678	Often
9) I integrate assistive technology tools to enhance the learning experience of students in inclusive classrooms.	3.10	0.771	Often
10) I encourage buddy systems for peer support in student collaboration.	3.30	0.577	Often
Overall mean	3.26	0.431	Often
Legend: 3.51-4.00 = Always; 2.51-3.50 = Often; 1.51-2.50 = Seldom; 1.00-1.51 = Never			

Table 5 shows the interventions employer by teachers during the transition process as to academic performance. As seen on the table above, ten (10) indicators were used to evaluate the employed intervention specifically focused on the academic performance of the students during the transition process.

Based on the data gathered from the respondents, it was decided that an overall mean of 3.26 was computed which indicates that the respondents often employed the interventions stated in the table during transition process. Specifically, among the indicators presented in the table, the most commonly used intervention focused on the academic performance of the students was making use of visual aids to enhance retention and understanding in support to diverse learners which is presented in item no. 5. This intervention obtained the highest computed mean of 3.38 and was verbally interpreted as often. Whereas, the least employed intervention was using adaptive software to to facilitate smoother transitions for students with disabilities which is presented in item no. 6. This statement obtained a computed mean of 2.94 and was also interpreted as often employed.

The data gathered from the respondents on the interventions employed focused on the academic performance of their students during the transition process signifies that the teachers are more inclined in using traditional methods of teaching which make use of self-made visual aids for enhancing the students' retention. While, the incorporation of technology and teaching softwares are least commonly incorporated by the teachers as an intervention during the transition process. According to Shahzad *et al.*, (2020), it can help lessen behavioral issues because kids are less likely to feel stressed when they know what to anticipate from their academic path. For pupils to be able to adjust not just intellectually but also socially and emotionally, teachers must be able to establish a secure and friendly environment.

Table 6. Interventions employed as to behavioral development.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) I incorporate clear expectations with simple and positive language to create an inclusive environment.	3.24	0.625	Often
2) I provide extra time to students in activities they enjoy after displaying appropriate behavior.	3.21	0.552	Often
3) I use tokens and stickers to students after completing tasks and demonstrating positive behavior.	3.20	0.644	Often
4) I use non-verbal cues to redirect attention to prevent embarrassment and keep the student engaged.	3.28	0.665	Often
5) I provide opportunities for role-play or simulations of new environments to prepare students.	3.30	0.599	Often
6) I use assistive tools during high stimulation periods to promote a calmer and focused environment.	3.06	0.790	Often
7) I gradually expose students to new environments or settings to ease behavioral adjustment.	3.27	0.616	Often
8) I monitor and document behavioral progress before, during, and after transitions.	3.31	0.579	Often
9) I seek support from school special education professionals when necessary.	3.41	0.590	Often
10) I collaborate with parents or guardians to address student behavior concerns.	3.44	0.594	Often
Overall mean	3.27	0.418	Often
Legend: 3.51-4.00 = Always; 2.51-3.50 = Often; 1.51-2.50 = Seldom; 1.00-1.51 = Never			

The interventions employed by teachers during transition process as to behavioral development was also determined in the study using ten (10) indicators. As seen from Table 6 an overall mean of 3.27 was computed from the statements that were evaluated by the respondents. This result signifies that the interventions presented in the table for behavioral development were often employed by the teachers.

In accordance to this, among the given indicators in the table, the most commonly used intervention that was focuses on behavioral development was collaborating with parents or guardians to address student behavior concerns which was evident in item no. 10 which had a computed mean of 3.44 and was verbally interpreted as often employed. Aside from this, the least commonly used intervention for behavioral development was from item no. 6 in which teachers use assistive tools during high stimulation periods to promote a calmer and focused environment. This statement obtained a computed mean of 3.06 and is still considered as often employed by the respondents using the verbal interpretation scale.

The findings suggest that teachers consistently implement interventions to support students' behavioral development during the transition process. These interventions are generally practiced on a regular basis,

indicating that teachers recognize the importance of addressing behavioral concerns alongside academic adjustments.

Among the various strategies, collaborating with parents or guardians emerged as the most prominent, underscoring the vital role of home-school partnerships in effectively managing student behavior. On the other hand, the use of assistive tools during high-stimulation periods appeared to be the least emphasized, which may reflect certain challenges such as limited resources, lack of training, or lower prioritization compared to other interventions.

The efficacy of these interventions is corroborated by existing literature. A study by Kausik and Hussain (2023) indicates that inclusive education has a positive effect on academic motivation and self-efficacy in students with learning disabilities. The research indicates that students in inclusive settings demonstrate greater academic motivation than their peers in segregated environments, implying that the inclusive strategies utilized by teachers in Dasmariñas may be fostering comparable positive outcomes. It corresponds with the noted prevalence of academic interventions in the present study.

The study's consistent application of behavioral interventions aligns with findings from the Child Health and Development Institute's initiatives in Connecticut schools, where a transition to restorative practices has resulted in enhanced student behavior and a decrease in suspensions (CT Insider, 2024). These practices focus on comprehending and tackling underlying issues instead of resorting to punitive measures, reflecting the proactive behavioral strategies utilized by educators in Dasmariñas. This alignment with evidence-based practices indicates that the interventions employed are both prevalent and rooted in methods demonstrated to effectively promote positive behavioral changes.

Extent of Implementation of Interventions as to Academic Performance and Behavioral Development

Table 7 presents the extent of implementation of interventions as to academic performance. An overall mean of 3.31 was computed from the ten (10) indicators shown in the table. This result indicates that the implementation of the interventions for academic performance is incorporated to a great extent. To specify, among the given indicators in the table, it was revealed that the most commonly implemented intervention was simplifying instructions in assessing to accommodate the needs of students with disabilities and coordinating with parents or guardians to support students' academic progress at home from items no. 5 and 10 since both statements gained the highest computed mean of 3.41 and were interpreted to be implemented to a great extent.

Table 7. Extent of implementation as to academic performance.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) I provide alternative assignments or projects based on students' abilities and interest.	3.21	0.591	Great extent
2) I implement step-by-step instruction as scaffolding technique with visual aids mastering complex tasks.	3.33	0.609	Great extent
3) I provide remedial instruction for academic support to students with learning disabilities and difficulties.	3.35	0.627	Great extent
4) I allow extra and flexible time for activities, tests, and assignments to accommodate student needs.	3.33	0.633	Great extent
5) I simplify instructions in assessing to accommodate the needs of students with disabilities.	3.41	0.602	Great extent
6) I modify instruction based on student performance and feedback to accommodate students with learning disabilities.	3.38	0.597	Great extent
7) I integrate visual, auditory, and kinesthetic learning materials to support diverse learners.	3.32	0.676	Great extent
8) I collaborate with special education teachers to enhance student learning.	3.28	0.594	Great extent
9) I attend training and workshop sessions for professional development on inclusive teaching.	3.13	0.836	Great extent
10) I coordinate with parents or guardians to support students' academic progress at home	3.41	0.603	Great extent
Overall mean	3.31	0.434	Great extent
Legend: 3.51-4.00 = Very great extent; 2.51-3.50 = Great extent; 1.51-2.50 = Low extent; 1.00-1.51 = Very low extent			

While the least commonly implemented intervention was attending training and workshop sessions for professional development on inclusive teaching from item no. 9 since this gained the lowest computed mean of 3.13. Despite being the lowest computed mean, this intervention was still viewed to be implemented to a great extent.

The findings imply that teachers implement interventions to enhance students' academic performance to a considerable extent. This demonstrates that strategies supporting inclusive and effective teaching are regularly incorporated into classroom practices.

Notably, simplifying instructions to accommodate the needs of students with disabilities and coordinating with parents or guardians emerged as the most emphasized interventions. This highlights the teachers' commitment to addressing diverse learning needs and the importance they place on home-school collaboration in promoting academic success.

Meanwhile, attending professional development through training and workshops on inclusive teaching appeared to be the least emphasized. Although still practiced, this suggests that opportunities for continuous professional growth in inclusive strategies may not be as frequently pursued or available compared to classroom-based and family-centered interventions.

Muega (2016) asserts that inclusive education has been promoted as a solution to the educational inequalities that children with special needs encounter. Compared to the conventional paradigm, which frequently placed disabled children in specialized programs like special education (SPED) schools, this represents a substantial change. Although there are still obstacles in the way of its complete implementation, Muega's study sheds light on the viewpoints of educators, administrators, and parents and shows a general drive for inclusivity.

Table 8. Extent of implementation as to behavioral development.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) I encourage peer modeling to influence positive behavior in the classroom.	3.36	0.566	Great extent
2) I track and document behavioral incidents to monitor progress and inform interventions.	3.21	0.603	Great extent
3) I implement rewards to students after demonstrating positive behavior.	3.36	0.629	Great extent
4) I use hand signals as non-verbal cues to manage classroom behavior discreetly.	3.24	0.696	Great extent
5) I provide frequent breaks or movement opportunities to minimize behavioral issues.	3.31	0.629	Great extent
6) I create a calm-down corner or safe space for students to manage their emotions.	3.05	0.785	Great extent
7) I adjust classroom seating or grouping arrangements to minimize behavioral issues.	3.30	0.659	Great extent
8) I provide immediate and specific feedback on behavior to help students understand consequences.	3.33	0.623	Great extent
9) I see support from school special education professionals when necessary.	3.35	0.564	Great extent
10) I recognize and address early signs of behavioral escalation to prevent disruptive incidents.	3.36	0.618	Great extent
Overall mean	3.29	0.428	Great extent
Legend: 3.51-4.00 = Very great extent; 2.51-3.50 = Great extent; 1.51-2.50 = Low extent; 1.00-1.51 = Very low extent			

The extent of implementation of interventions as to behavioral development was also evaluated in the study and was shown in table 8. Ten (10) indicators were also used to determine the interventions as to behavioral development were implemented during transition. Based on the data gathered from the respondents, it was determined that an overall mean of 3.29 from their responses signifies that the interventions as to behavioral development was implemented to a great extent. In connection to this, among the indicators presented in the table, it was found out that encouraging peer modeling, implementing rewards to students after demonstrating positive behavior, and recognizing and addressing early signs of behavioral escalation to

prevent disruptive incidents were the most commonly implemented interventions which was viewed to be implemented to a great extent since both statements obtained the highest computed mean of 3.36. While, the least commonly implemented intervention as to behavioral development was creating a calm-down corner or safe space for students to manage their emotions since this gained a computed mean of 3.05 however, this intervention was still implemented to a great extent based on the responses of the respondents.

The findings imply that teachers implement interventions for behavioral development to a considerable extent during the transition process. This indicates that managing student behavior is a consistent priority for teachers and that they integrate various strategies to foster a positive and supportive classroom environment. Among the strategies, the most emphasized were the use of rewards to reinforce positive behavior and the early recognition of behavioral concerns to prevent disruptions. These results highlight teachers' proactive and preventive approaches in shaping desirable student conduct.

On the other hand, creating a calm-down corner or safe space for students was the least emphasized intervention. Although still practiced, this suggests that such strategies may be less prioritized or that schools may face challenges in terms of space, resources, or awareness in consistently implementing them. The existing literature supports the effectiveness of these interventions. Capangpangan *et al.*, (2023) highlights the significance of teacher preparation and support in the implementation of inclusive education, indicating that variables such as educational attainment, teaching experience, and involvement in pertinent training help in the effective application of inclusive interventions. The consistent application of interventions by teachers in Dasmariñas commonly correlated with their continuous professional learning program and commitment to inclusive education principles.

The implementation of behavioral interventions is consistent with the school-wide positive behavioral interventions and supports (SWPBIS) framework, which focuses on proactive strategies to encourage positive behavior and mitigate challenging behaviors in inclusive environments. Implementing evidence-based strategies enables educators to effectively manage behavioral issues, thereby fostering a responsive learning environment for all students. The findings of the study highlight the importance of ongoing professional development and the implementation of established frameworks to improve the effectiveness of inclusive education practices.

Level of Effectiveness of Interventions as to Academic Performance and Behavioral Development

Table 9. Level of effectiveness as to academic performance.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) Adapting lesson plans to accommodate diverse learning needs leading to improved grades and engagement.	3.34	0.601	Effective
2) Structural step-by-step instructions with visuals results to better understand complex tasks.	3.36	0.629	Effective
3) Multiples assessment methods helped learners with special educational needs express understanding more confidently.	3.32	0.687	Effective
4) Flexible time frames for task completion results in better task completion and quality of work.	3.39	0.611	Effective
5) Incorporating visual aids enhanced retention of lessons and comprehension of students.	3.50	0.609	Effective
6) Remedial as additional academic support helped struggling students make noticeable progress in academic.	3.33	0.644	Effective
7) Modified assessment of students with special needs increase accuracy in answering questions and reflection of learning.	3.44	0.631	Effective
8) Teacher training programs improve preparedness for inclusive strategies resulting to improved academic outcomes.	3.50	0.645	Effective
9) Collaboration with SPED teachers improve the alignment of instruction to learners with special educational needs.	3.48	0.571	Effective
10) Assistive technology integration in lesson plans increased student dependence and improved task completion.	3.34	0.625	Effective
Overall mean	3.39	0.454	Effective
Legend: 3.51–4.00 = Very effective; 2.51–3.50 = Effective; 1.51–2.50 = Less effective; 1.00–1.51 = Not effective			

Table 9 highlights the level of effectiveness of interventions as to academic performance. A total of ten (10) indicators were also used to assess the responses of the chosen participants of the study. The data gathered from the respondents revealed that the interventions employed as to academic performance was effective considering an overall mean of 3.39.

Specifically, among the given statements, item no. 5 which states incorporating visual aids enhanced retention of lessons and comprehension of students and item no. 8 which states teacher training programs improve preparedness for inclusive strategies resulting to improved academic outcomes were the most commonly viewed intervention that is effective with regards to academic performance since both statements obtained the highest computed mean of 3.50. While the least commonly viewed intervention that is effective was multiples assessment methods helped learners with special educational needs express understanding more confidently which gained a computed mean of 3.32.

The findings imply that the interventions employed by teachers to support academic performance were generally effective. This reflects that the strategies being implemented contribute meaningfully to improving students' learning outcomes, particularly in inclusive classroom settings.

Among the interventions, the use of visual aids to enhance lesson retention and comprehension, as well as participation in teacher training programs to strengthen preparedness for inclusive strategies, were identified as the most effective. This highlights the dual importance of instructional tools that directly support student learning and continuous professional development that equips teachers with the skills to address diverse academic needs.

Meanwhile, the use of multiple assessment methods to help learners with special educational needs express understanding more confidently was considered the least effective. Although still viewed positively, this suggests that assessment practices may require further refinement, adaptation, or support to maximize their impact on diverse learners.

In the study analyzing the various outcomes of multisensory learning, Rau *et al.*, (2020) noted that high efficiency was obtained with minimal effort for students and teachers, minimizing the distraction for individuals. Harrison and Patel (2023) suggest that involving children in hands-on activities, music, and visual storytelling fosters deeper understanding and long-term retention.

Table 10. Level of effectiveness as to behavioral development.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) Consistently enforcement of classroom rules and expectations leading to calmer classroom.	3.38	0.584	Effective
2) Using positive reinforcement (e.g., praise, rewards) increases learners' confidence and courage to keep making positive behavior.	3.44	0.607	Effective
3) Individualized behavior support plans for students with behavioral needs lead to positive interaction and fewer disruptions.	3.39	0.600	Effective
4) Teaching social skills (e.g., cooperation, empathy, conflict resolution) to all students builds a supportive classroom environment resulting.	3.46	0.557	Effective
5) Behavior contracts or goal setting increase motivation leading to improving self-control decreasing negative behavior.	3.47	0.583	Effective
6) Self-monitoring and reflection on behavior builds self-awareness in making positive choices in recognizing learners' progress.	3.34	0.575	Effective
7) Safe space corner supports emotional regulation allowing learners to reduce outbursts and focus on learning.	3.37	0.583	Effective
8) Collaborating with parents/guardians to address behavioral concerns leads to behavior improvement in home and school.	3.46	0.583	Effective
9) Consultation with guidance counselors or behavioral specialists for support leads to significant decrease in challenging behaviors.	3.45	0.556	Effective
10) Clear routines and consistent structure in managing classroom behavior help students feel secure leading to fewer behavior issues.	3.53	0.584	Effective
Overall mean	3.42	0.409	Effective
Legend: 3.51–4.00 = Very effective; 2.51–3.50 = Effective; 1.51–2.50 = Less effective; 1.00–1.51 = Not effective			

Table 10 presents the level of effectiveness of interventions as to behavioral development which also made use of ten (10) indicators that are used to evaluate the responses of the participants of the study. Based on the data gathered from the respondents, an overall mean of 3.42 implies that the interventions for behavioral development were viewed to be effective by the respondents.

In relation to this, among the given statements, clear routines and consistent structure in managing classroom behavior help students feel secure leading to fewer behavior issues from item no. 10 was deemed to be the most common intervention that was effective as to behavioral development since this statement gained the highest computed mean of 3.53. While the least common effective intervention was self-monitoring and reflection on behavior builds self-awareness in making positive choices in recognizing learners' progress from item no. 6 which obtained the lowest computed mean of 3.34.

The findings imply that the interventions employed for behavioral development were generally effective in supporting students during the transition process. This reflects that teachers' strategies contribute positively to creating structured, supportive, and well-managed classroom environments. Among the interventions, establishing clear routines and consistent structures was found to be the most effective in managing classroom behavior. This underscores the importance of predictability and stability in helping students feel secure, which in turn minimizes behavioral issues.

On the other hand, strategies that emphasize self-monitoring and reflection on behavior, while still effective, were considered less impactful compared to other interventions. This suggests that although fostering self-awareness is valuable, it may require additional guidance, reinforcement, or age-appropriate approaches for learners to fully benefit from such practices. A study by Tuero *et al.*, (2022) investigated the effect of school-based training in self-regulation learning strategies on students' academic performance. The research indicated that these interventions had a beneficial impact on student performance in multiple subjects, highlighting the significance of organized and focused approaches in improving academic results. Obee *et al.*, (2022) performed a systematic review examining professional development programs aimed at enhancing classroom management and behavioral support skills in early childhood environments. The review indicated that effective training programs for educators markedly enhanced their capacity to manage classroom behaviors, resulting in improved student behavioral outcomes.

Degree of Challenges Encountered by Teachers as to Academic Performance and Behavioral Development

Table 11. Degree of challenges encountered as to academic performance.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) I find it challenging to modify lesson plans to accommodate students with different learning abilities.	3.27	0.725	Agree
2) I lack sufficient training or resources to teach effectively in an inclusive classroom.	3.21	0.725	Agree
3) Limited access to resources and teaching aids affects my ability to support academic performance.	3.29	0.679	Strongly agree
4) I struggle to foster positive peer relationships among students in an inclusive classroom.	3.24	0.796	Agree
5) Large class sizes make it challenging to provide individualized academic support.	3.46	0.720	Agree
6) Limited time for planning and preparing adapted materials hinders academic support.	3.29	0.690	Agree
7) Monitoring and tracking academic progress of students with special needs is time-consuming and challenging.	3.39	0.753	Agree
8) The lack of teaching assistants or aids affects my ability to provide one-on-one support.	3.36	0.719	Agree
9) I struggle to maintain student engagement during academic activities in an inclusive setup.	3.28	0.769	Agree
10) Encouraging collaboration between students with and without disabilities is a significant challenge.	3.31	0.640	Agree
Overall mean	3.31	0.552	Agree
Legend: 3.51–4.00 = Strongly agree; 2.51–3.50 = Agree; 1.51–2.50 = Disagree; 1.00–1.51 = Strongly disagree			

The degree of challenges encountered by teachers as to academic performance was also evaluated in the study using ten (10) indicators which are presented in the above table. Based on the data gathered from the respondents, it was viewed that the respondents agreed on the challenges presented in the given table considering the overall mean of 3.31 which was computed from their responses.

Specifically, among the given indicators in the table, the most common challenge experienced by the respondents was large class sizes which make it challenging to provide individualized academic support since this obtained the highest computed mean of 3.46. While the least common challenges experienced by the respondents was lacking sufficient training or resources to teach effectively in an inclusive classroom since this obtained the lowest computed mean of 3.21.

The findings imply that teachers encounter notable challenges in supporting students' academic performance, particularly within inclusive classroom settings. These challenges are generally acknowledged by the respondents, reflecting the realities teachers face in balancing instructional demands with diverse learner needs. Among the challenges, managing large class sizes was identified as the most significant concern. This highlights the difficulty teachers experience in providing individualized academic support when student-to-teacher ratios are high, limiting their ability to address specific learning needs effectively.

Meanwhile, the least emphasized challenge was the lack of sufficient training or resources for inclusive teaching. Although still recognized as a concern, this suggests that teachers may have some level of access to professional development and resources, or that they prioritize other challenges, such as class size, as being more pressing in their practice.

Table 12. Degree of challenges encountered as to behavioral development.

Indicators	Mean	SD	VI
1) It is challenging to manage classroom behavior while addressing diverse academic needs.	3.33	0.609	Agree
2) I face challenges in communicating effectively with parents of students with special needs.	3.31	0.717	Agree
3) I find it challenging to address bullying or social discrimination among students with diverse needs.	3.30	0.726	Agree
4) I feel emotionally drained from balancing the needs of all students effectively.	3.25	0.750	Agree
5) I receive little to no follow-up support after reporting behavioral concerns.	3.30	0.766	Agree
6) I receive inadequate support from parents/guardians in managing students' behavior.	3.23	0.801	Agree
7) I lack sufficient time to observe, document, and analyze student behavior.	3.32	0.779	Agree
8) Emotional outbursts or meltdowns disrupt classroom routines and affect learning time.	3.30	0.715	Agree
9) I struggle to engage students with behavioral difficulties in classroom activities.	3.29	0.732	Agree
10) I face difficulty building trust and rapport with students exhibiting challenging behavior.	3.27	0.830	Agree
Overall mean	3.29	0.562	Agree
Legend: 3.51–4.00 = Strongly agree; 2.51–3.50 = Agree; 1.51–2.50 = Disagree; 1.00–1.51 = Strongly disagree			

Table 12 highlights the degree of challenges encountered by teachers as to behavioral development. Ten (10) indicators which were presented in the table were also used to assess the responses of the respondents. This revealed an overall mean of 3.29 in which it signifies that the respondents agree to the challenges presented in the table.

In connection to this, the most common challenges as to behavioral development was from item no. 1 in which it is challenging to manage classroom behavior while addressing diverse academic needs since this obtained the highest computed mean of 3.33. While the least common challenge experienced by the respondents as to behavioral management was feeling emotionally drained from balancing the needs of all students effectively since this gained the lowest computed mean of 3.25. The findings imply that teachers

encounter considerable challenges in managing students' behavioral development during the transition process. Respondents generally agreed with the difficulties presented, indicating that behavioral management remains a critical concern in inclusive classrooms.

The most pressing challenge identified was the difficulty of managing classroom behavior while simultaneously addressing diverse academic needs. This underscores the complex role teachers play in balancing both instructional and behavioral responsibilities, which can strain their capacity to maintain a supportive learning environment. On the other hand, the least emphasized challenge was the feeling of being emotionally drained from balancing the needs of all students. While still acknowledged, this suggests that teachers may be more focused on the immediate, practical aspects of managing classroom behavior rather than on their own emotional toll, or that they have developed coping mechanisms to manage stress.

Significant Difference in Implementation Based on Teacher Profile

Table 13. Significant difference in the extent of implementation employed by teachers when grouped according to profile.

Age	Extent of implementation as to academic performance	Extent of implementation as to behavioral development
Chi-square	10.309	5.464
df	3	3
Asymp. Sig	.016	.141
School	Extent of implementation as to academic performance	Extent of implementation as to behavioral development
Chi-square	6.143	12.542
df	4	4
Asymp. Sig	.189	0.14
Position	Extent of implementation as to academic performance	Extent of implementation as to behavioral development
Chi-square	9.613	9.167
df	6	6
Asymp. Sig	.142	.164
Length of service	Extent of implementation as to academic performance	Extent of implementation as to behavioral development
Chi-square	2.136	1.458
df	3	3
Asymp. Sig	.545	.692

The results imply that among the profile variables, only age had a significant influence on the extent of implementation in terms of academic performance. This suggests that teachers' practices in addressing academic outcomes may differ across age groups, possibly due to generational differences in pedagogical approaches, adaptability, and experience. In contrast, no significant differences were observed across school, position, and length of service, indicating that teachers generally employ similar strategies regardless of these factors.

A study by Izquierdo *et al.*, (2025) supports this observation, indicating that professional experience significantly impacts teachers' psychological well-being and self-efficacy, both of which are essential for effective teaching practices. The research highlights that although years of experience play a role in these attributes, the introduction of structured programs aimed at emotional intelligence and resilience can significantly improve teachers' competencies, independent of their age. It indicates that although age is an important factor, focused professional development can reduce age-related disparities in the effectiveness of intervention implementation.

A systematic review by Makhmetova *et al.*, (2023) underscores the significance of professional learning experiences in promoting teachers' development. The review demonstrates that both formal and informal professional development activities enhance teachers' adaptability and effectiveness in executing educational interventions.

Significant Difference in Level of Effectiveness

Table 14. Significant difference in the level of effectiveness of the interventions employed by teachers.

Age	Level of effectiveness as to academic performance	Level of effectiveness as to behavioral development
Chi-square	6.427	6.822
df	3	3
Asymp. Sig	0.93	0.78
School	Level of effectiveness as to academic performance	Level of effectiveness as to behavioral development
Chi-square	6.944	6.266
df	4	4
Asymp. Sig	.139	.180
Position	Level of effectiveness as to academic performance	Level of effectiveness as to behavioral development
Chi-square	13.255	12.684
df	6	6
Asymp. Sig	0.39	0.48
Length of service	Level of effectiveness as to academic performance	Level of effectiveness as to behavioral development
Chi-square	1.618	2.058
df	3	3
Asymp. Sig	.655	.560

The results imply that the effectiveness of interventions used by teachers does not significantly vary when grouped according to their age, school, position, or length of service. This suggests that the strategies applied are generally effective across different teacher profiles, reflecting consistency in practice and uniformity in their outcomes for both academic and behavioral dimensions.

The findings corroborate existing research highlighting the significance of teacher support in influencing student outcomes. Uzorka *et al.*, (2024) demonstrate that teacher professional development programs improve teaching quality and student achievement, regardless of the teacher's role. Research by Cabahug *et al.*, (2024) indicates that teaching experience and educational attainment moderately influence performance, highlighting the importance of continuous professional development for all teacher roles. The findings indicate that the effectiveness of interventions is influenced not only by a teacher's role but also by their continuous professional growth and development.

Significant Difference in Challenges Encountered by Teachers

Table 15. Significant difference in the degree of challenges encountered by the teachers.

Age	Challenges encountered as to academic performance	Challenges encountered as to behavioral development
Chi-square	8.904	10.533
df	3	3
Asymp. Sig	0.31	.015
School	Challenges encountered as to academic performance	Challenges encountered as to behavioral development
Chi-square	6.520	.967
df	4	4
Asymp. Sig	.164	.915
Position	Challenges encountered as to academic performance	Challenges encountered as to behavioral development
Chi-square	12.367	18.184
df	6	6
Asymp. Sig	.054	.006
Length of service	Challenges encountered as to academic performance	Challenges encountered as to behavioral development
Chi-square	5.703	3.886
df	3	3
Asymp. Sig	.127	.274

The results imply that challenges in academic performance are generally consistent across teacher profiles, while challenges in behavioral development are influenced by both age and position. These findings suggest that classroom management difficulties are not uniformly experienced and may depend on generational perspectives as well as the professional roles held by teachers. This highlights the need for differentiated support and training programs that address behavioral management strategies tailored to teachers' age groups and professional positions.

Supporting literature confirms these findings. Bakar *et al.*, (2022) found that teachers at different levels in Malaysian schools faced comparable challenges concerning workload, student engagement, and resource adequacy, highlighting the widespread nature of these issues. A study by Kim and Kim (2023) identified that challenges like classroom management and the balance between administrative duties and teaching responsibilities were consistently experienced by teachers across various roles. It indicates the necessity for institutional support systems to be both inclusive and comprehensive. These studies support the idea that effectively addressing teacher challenges necessitates comprehensive approaches that go beyond positional distinctions.

Relationship Between Implementation, Effectiveness, and Challenges

Table 16. Significant relationship between the extent of implementation, level of effectiveness, and degree of challenges encountered by the teachers.

		Interventions Employed as to Academic Performance	Interventions Employed as to Behavioral Development	Extent of Implementation as to Academic Performance	Extent of Implementation as to Behavioral Development	Level of Effectiveness as to Academic Performance	Level of Effectiveness as to Behavioral Development	Degree of Challenges Encountered as to Academic Performance	Overall Degree of Challenges Encountered as to Behavioral Development
Interventions Employed as to Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	1	.622**	.672**	.655**	.639**	.687**	.117	.032
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000	.000	.000	.000	.000	.177	.714
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Interventions Employed as to Behavioral Development	Pearson Correlation	.622**	1	.628**	.508**	.617**	.658**	.112	.012
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000		.000	.000	.000	.000	.195	.889
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Extent of Implementation as to Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.672**	.628**	1	.763**	.758**	.796**	.167	.100
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000		.000	.000	.000	.053	.249
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Extent of Implementation as to Behavioral Development	Pearson Correlation	.655**	.508**	.763**	1	.730**	.748**	.134	.066
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000		.000	.000	.121	.444
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Level of Effectiveness as to Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.639**	.617**	.758**	.730**	1	.799**	.234**	.205*
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000		.000	.006	.017
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Level of Effectiveness as to Behavioral Development	Pearson Correlation	.687**	.658**	.796**	.748**	.799**	1	.129	.073
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000		.135	.401
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Degree of Challenges Encountered as to Academic Performance	Pearson Correlation	.117	.112	.167	.134	.234**	.129	1	.811**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.177	.195	.053	.121	.006	.135		.000
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135
Degree of Challenges Encountered as to Behavioral Development	Pearson Correlation	.032	.012	.100	.066	.205*	.073	.811**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.714	.889	.249	.444	.017	.401	.000	
	N	135	135	135	135	135	135	135	135

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed); * . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results imply that successful program implementation is closely tied to effectiveness but is also accompanied by inevitable challenges. As implementation increases, effectiveness improves, yet challenges also become more pronounced. This highlights the importance of providing adequate support mechanisms, training opportunities, and resource allocation to teachers and parents to sustain the program's gains while managing the difficulties that arise.

Declarations

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References

1. Albion, P.R., Tondeur, J., Forkosh-Baruch, A. and Peeraer, J. 2015. Teachers' professional development for ICT integration: Towards a reciprocal relationship between research and practice. *Education and Information Technologies*, 20(4): 655-673.
2. Bakar, A.R.A., Ahmad, R. and Ismail, Z. 2022. Exploring challenges faced by school teachers in Malaysia: Workload and resource issues. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 31(2): 278-283.
3. Bas, A., Burns, N., Gulotta, A., Junker, J., Drasler, B., Lehner, R., et al. 2021. Understanding the development, standardization, and validation process of alternative in vitro test methods for regulatory approval from a researcher perspective. *Small*, 17: 2006027.
4. Bessarab, A., Antonenko, I., Turubarova, A., Smoliak, V. and Morenko, O. 2023. Inclusive education: Strategies and methods of implementation in the context of modern pedagogy. *Cadernos de Educação Tecnologia e Sociedade*, 16(se2): 165-177.
5. Cabahug, I., Osias, N.C., Ongcachuy, B.L. and Corpuz, G.G. 2024. 21st century skills and teachers' performance: Basis for instructional development plan. *American Journal of Arts and Human Science*, 3(2): 82-105.
6. Capangpangan, S.E., Tango-an, J.M. and Lumapas, R.Z. 2023. Teachers' preparation and support in the implementation of inclusive education for learners with exceptionalities. *International Journal of Inclusive and Sustainable Education*, 2(6): 244-273.
7. Child Health and Development Institute of Connecticut (CHDI). 2024. Restorative approaches in schools: Promoting equity and reducing exclusionary discipline. Issue Brief. <https://www.chdi.org/>
8. CT Insider. 2024. Connecticut schools shift toward restorative practices to improve student behavior. <https://www.ctinsider.com>
9. Dada, S., Wilder, J., May, A., Klang, N. and Pillay, M. 2023. A review of interventions for children and youth with severe disabilities in inclusive education. *Cogent Education*, 10(2): 2278359.
10. Izquierdo, A., Pozo-Rico, T., Pérez-Rico, C., Fernández-García, C., Castejón, J.L. and Gilar-Corbi, R. 2025. Effectiveness of a training program on the psychological well-being and self-efficacy of active teachers, controlling for gender and experience. *Education Sciences*, 15(3): 382.
11. Kausik, N.H. and Hussain, D. 2023. The impact of inclusive education on academic motivation, academic self-efficacy, and well-being of students with learning disability. *Journal of Education*, 203(2): 251-257.
12. Kim, Y. and Kim, J. 2023. Teacher workload and its impact on teaching effectiveness: Evidence from South Korea. *Educational Studies*, 49(4): 512-529.
13. Mabanag, R., Delicana, A., Igot, P.E., Sitoy, R., Tandag, J. and Mangubat, R. 2024. Teacher readiness and challenges in inclusive classrooms. *World Journal on Education and Humanities Research*, 4(4): 180-192.

14. Makhmetova, Z., Karabassova, L., Zhakim, A. and Karinov, A. 2025. Exploring the effects of professional learning experiences on in-service teachers' growth: A systematic review of literature. *Education Sciences*, 15(2): 146.
15. Mays, D., Jindal-Snape, D. and Boyle, C. 2020. Chapter 10 transitions of children with additional support needs across stages. In: *Inclusive education: Global issues and controversies*, 163-178p.
16. Muega, M.A.G. 2016. Inclusive education in the Philippines: Through the eyes of teachers, administrators, and parents of children with special needs. *Social Science Diliman*, 12(1): 5-28.
17. Ngadni, I., Singh, G.K.S., Ahmad, I.Y.B. and Baharudin, S.N.A. 2023. Challenges faced by teachers in inclusive classrooms in early childhood education (ECE) setting. *International Journal of Academic Research in Progressive Education and Development*, 12(2): 1635-1649.
18. Obee, A.F., Hart, K.C. and Fabiano, G.A. 2022. Professional development targeting classroom management and behavioral support skills in early childhood settings: A systematic review. *School Mental Health*, 15(2): 339-369.
19. Perera, U. 2024. Strategies used by the teachers who are in inclusion classrooms regarding the students with special educational needs. *International Journal of Research and Innovation in Applied Science*, IX: 126-133.
20. Pradhan, K.C. and Naik, M.S. 2024. Inclusive education: A foundation for equality and empowerment at the elementary stage. *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research in Arts, Science and Technology*, 2(2): 1-8.
21. Rau, P.L.P., Zheng, J. and Wei, Y. 2020. Distractive effect of multimodal information in multisensory learning. *Computers and Education*, 144: 103699.
22. Shahzad, A., Seema, S. and Reba, A. 2020. Effects of classroom transition techniques on students' behavior at secondary level. *Journal of Entrepreneurship Education*, 23(5): 1-7.
23. Shams, L. and Seitz, A.R. 2008. Benefits of multisensory learning. *Trends in Cognitive Sciences*, 12(11): 411-417.
24. Tabassum, N. and Nayak, B.S. 2021. Gender stereotypes and their impact on women's career progressions from a managerial perspective. *IIM Kozhikode Society and Management Review*, 10(2): 192-208.
25. Then, D. and Pohlmann-Rother, S. 2024. (Multi-)professional cooperation in the transition of children with disabilities to school: Cooperation processes from the point of view of the skilled workers. *Journal of Educational Sciences*, 27(4): 923-952.
26. Tuero, E., Núñez, J.C., Vallejo, G., Fernández, M.P., Añón, F.J., Moreira, T., Martins, J. and Rosário, P. 2022. Short and long-term effects on academic performance of a school-based training in self-regulation learning: A three-level experimental study. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13: 889201.
27. Uzorka, A., Kalabuki, K. and Odebiyi, O.A. 2024. The effectiveness of in-service teacher training programs in enhancing teaching quality and student achievement. *Forum for Education Studies*, 2(3): 1465.
28. Woodcock, S. and Hardy, I. 2023. Teacher self-efficacy, inclusion and professional development practices: Cultivating a learning environment for all. *Professional Development in Education*, 1-15.

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